

UCC Chemical Society 100 Year Anniversary

Report by: S. Timony*

Event Date: 06/03/2025

Venue: Cork County Cricket Club

Event Type: Social Event, Other
(Centenary)

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Organising Committee: J. Hennessy (Chair)^a, S. Lane (Vice Chair)^a, B. Chan (Finance Officer)^a, K. Keohane (Secretary)^a, S. Timony (CPRO)^a, K. Carvello (GPRO)^a, J. Daly (Ex-Officio)^a, C. Cody (Industry and Education Officer)^a, C. Rafferty (Events Officer)^a, S. O'Mahony (First Year Rep)^a, M. McGrath (First Year Rep)^a, L. Kelleher (Second Year Rep)^a, S. Fitzharris (Third Year Rep)^a, R. Brown (Fourth Year Rep)^a, T. McInerney (Post-Grad Rep)^a

^a University College Cork

Organisation: UCC Chemical Society

Event Sponsors

Royal Society of Chemistry Republic of Ireland Local Section

Summary

When UCC Chemical Society was founded in 1925, it was the first university chemical society in Ireland. The society has now spent a century fostering a love of chemistry and strengthening student-staff relationships in University College Cork (UCC). On 6th March 2025, a centenary event was held in Cork County Cricket Club in order to commemorate this milestone and to honour the many members who have shaped the society over the course of 100 years. The formal gathering brought together current and former members, as well as staff and students of UCC School of Chemistry for an evening of refreshments, discussions, and reflections on the society's legacy and the shared chemistry community in Cork. Speeches from current Chairperson James Hennessy, as well as former chair Dr. John O'Donoghue (RSC) and former member Prof. Anita Maguire (Head of UCC School of Chemistry), recounted the society's long and rich history and explored the impact the society has had on each speaker. This event provided an opportunity for students and staff, as well as past and current members of the society to foster connections and strengthen existing relationships.

Attendees

In total there were 109 attendees. This included 2 guest speakers (Prof. Anita Maguire and Dr. John O'Donoghue) as well as the 15 UCC Chemical Society committee members. The rest of the guests included lecturers, undergraduate students and postgraduate students from the UCC School of Chemistry, as well as Chemical society alumni and past students of the School of Chemistry. A group of these past students are now working in industry.

Target audience: academics, undergraduates, postgraduates, industrialists, retired members, members of the public, past and current members of UCC Chemical Society, past and current staff and students of UCC School of Chemistry

Programme

Table 1. List of speakers.

Time	Speaker	Affiliation
20:15	James Hennessy	UCC Chemical Society
20:30	Prof. Anita Maguire	University College Cork
20:45	Dr John O'Donoghue	RSC Education Coordinator

Proceedings

The evening began at 19:00 with a formal drinks reception at Cork County Cricket Club, giving attendees an opportunity to mingle and speak to one another. Guests were encouraged to sample the buffet of food on offer. At 20:15 speeches began, first with James Hennessy, current Chairperson of the UCC Chemical Society welcoming attendees and introducing the evening, as well as giving an account of the history of the society. This was followed by speeches from Prof. Anita Maguire and Dr. John O'Donoghue, both former members of the society in which they recounted their experience as a part of the UCC Chemical Society and reflected on the impact of the society over the years. Following the speeches, a raffle was held, giving guests the opportunity to win some fantastic prizes. Prizes were sponsored by local businesses including Keane's Jewellers, College Road Pharmacy, Molaga Honey, O'Flynn's Gourmet Sausage Company, Lloyds Pharmacy, Fota Wildlife Park, The Rock Bar and Four Star Pizza. At 21:30, a 100th "birthday" cake was cut and distributed by Sarah Lane, Vice-Chairperson of the society in order to celebrate the centenary event. Attendees continued to socialise and form connections until the end of the event at midnight.

UCC Chemical Society

UCC Chemical Society aims to promote chemistry as a subject within the university as a whole, promote the integration between staff and students, both undergraduates and postgraduates, in the School of Chemistry through social and academic events and hold social, academic and career focused events catered to both postgraduates and undergraduates.

Figure 1. Speakers (left to right) Dr. John O'Donoghue (RSC), Prof. Anita Maguire (UCC), James Hennessy (UCC Chemical Society)

Figure 2. UCC Chemical Society Committee

Feedback

"Really impressed with what the society managed to achieve" - Prof. Anita Maguire, UCC School of Chemistry

Figure 3. Raffle Winners

Acknowledgements

UCC Chemical Society would like to formally extend our thanks to the Royal Society of Chemistry Local Chapter for sponsoring and advertising the event, as well as UCC School of Chemistry for promoting the event to staff and students. We would also like to thank Keane's Jewellers, College Road Pharmacy, Molaga Honey, O' Flynn's Gourmet Sausage Company, Lloyds Pharmacy, Fota Wildlife Park, The Rock Bar and Four Star Pizza for providing raffle prizes.